

Factors Affecting the Interlaminar Fracture Energy of Graphite/Epoxy Laminates

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ABSTRACT

The delamination fracture energy of graphite/epoxy composites has been examined utilizing a fracture mechanics approach. The material of primary interest was Hercules AS1/3501-6 with comparison testing on HMS/3501-6 and GY70/5208. The principal variables were moisture content, temperature and ply orientation. Both mode I opening and mode II shear stress fields were applied to specimens containing teflon strip notches.

In mode I, the crack initiation energy for AS1/3501-6 was essentially insensitive to the test variables and approximated values reported for bulk epoxy resins. On the other hand, weak interfacial fiber-matrix bonds in both HMS/3501-6 and GY70/5208 led to substantially reduced fracture toughness characteristics.

Crack extension in mode I resulted in enhanced fracture energies due primarily to fiber bridging. The maximum or stabilized energy was strongly dependent upon temperature, moisture and ply orientation in the delamination plane. Low temperature (-50°C)/dry conditions produced the lowest stabilized fracture toughness values whereas the greatest toughness corresponded to hot/wet conditions. Cross-ply orientations also produced significant increases in the crack extension resistance.

The mode II shear crack initiation energy for AS1/3501-6 was approximately three times greater than in mode I. An increase in matrix microcracking appeared to be the primary mechanism responsible for the enhanced resistance to cracking. The low fiber-matrix bond strength in HMS/3501-6 again resulted in a significantly lower fracture energy.

In contrast to mode I behaviour, the fracture energy for crack extension in mode II was less than that for initiation. Temperature and ply orientation effects were also less pronounced than in the mode I case.

INTRODUCTION

The majority of studies concerned with the fracture toughness of graphite/epoxy composites have assumed that the predominant crack propagation modes in structures will be translaminar (1). The extremely low fracture energies characteristic of mode I opening tensile fracture parallel to the fibers of 0.2 KJ/m² compared to those orthogonal to the fibers of 20 KJ/m² (2)(3) clearly emphasizes the need for cross-ply layups in structures in order to achieve acceptable translaminar fracture toughness behaviour. To a good approximation, Cruse (4) found that a rule of mixtures type formulation could predict the toughness of a (0/±45/90) layup given the toughness values for the individual plies.

More recently, the significance of interlaminar cracking or delamination as a primary composite fracture mode and not merely a secondary one has become apparent from several works (5)(6)(7)(8)(9). Growth of interlaminar defects can occur under tensile, compressive or shear loading due to the presence of induced interlaminar stresses, particularly in the vicinity of holes, surface scratches and free edges. Interlaminar defects are introduced with relative ease from low energy impact as well as during manufacture and assembly of composite structures. Furthermore, unlike the case for translaminar crack growth, interlaminar planes of weakness will exist in all layups until some means of interplanar reinforcement is devised. Clearly, interlaminar fracture toughness is a major factor in determining the damage tolerance of composite materials.

Most of the work reported to date on delamination fracture of graphite/epoxy has been concerned with the opening mode I tensile crack extension in ambient temperature/dry environments. Little attention has been given to mode II shear fracture (10) and to the effects of environments (moisture, temperature) which are known to degrade epoxy matrix composites in general and to ply orientation.

In the present paper we report the preliminary results of an experimental fracture mechanics approach to characterizing the interlaminar fracture toughness of graphite/epoxy subjected to either mode I or mode II stress fields. The principal variables studied were absorbed moisture content, temperature and ply orientation. Hercules AS1/3501-6 material was the primary composite examined with limited comparisons made on HMS/3501-6 and GY70/5208 materials. The former two systems are utilized extensively on the F-18 Hornet fighter aircraft.

EXPERIMENTAL

Prepreg layups were prepared with teflon-coated fabric strips inserted at appropriate locations on the midplane in order to act as controlled crack starters. The manufacturers' recommended curing cycles were followed and the laminates were postcured—177°C for eight hours. The nature and dimensions of the specimens cut from the laminates are shown in Figure 1.

Moisture conditioning was carried out at 75°C and 100% relative humidity until saturation (greater than three months). All 20°C tests were conducted at ambient humidity; the 100°C tests were done in boiling water and the -50°C tests were performed in an ethanol/water mixture. The dry state corresponded to specimens which had been maintained in a desiccator subsequent to the post-cure treatment and removed immediately prior to testing.

The approach adopted in order to assess the fracture toughness was the experimental compliance technique for the fracture energy or strain energy release rate, G_c (11).

The mode I Double Cantilever Beam (DCB) specimen was loaded through aluminum tabs bonded onto the ends. A series of loading/unloading steps were performed on each specimen, each step resulting in approximately 3 mm of crack growth. The crack length, a , was measured on both polished edges with a low power microscope and the compliance, C , was obtained from the load versus crack opening curves. A third degree polynomial was fitted to the C versus a values by the method of

least squares and dC/da calculated for insertion into the IRWIN strain energy release rate relationship,

$$G_{IC} = \frac{P^2}{2b} \frac{dC}{da} \quad (1)$$

where P is the critical load for crack extension and b the specimen width.

The mode II forward shear specimen was subjected to 3-point flexural loading in a manner that placed the teflon starter notch tip midway between the loading pins. As the notch faces in the vicinity of the outer loading pin would be either teflon-teflon or teflon-graphite, the frictional forces opposing sliding have been shown to be negligible (12). A similar specimen geometry but with the teflon starter lying entirely between the loading pins was adopted by Chatterjee and Pipes (10).

The mode II fracture energy was determined from equation (1) utilizing a compliance versus crack length relationship derived from a beam theory analysis (12). This was necessitated by the fact that experimental dC/da values were found to be subject to large errors due to the small variation in C with a at small a values. The compliance can be expressed in the form,

$$C = \frac{2L^3 + 3a^3}{8Eb h^3} \quad (2)$$

A comparison between C calculated from equation (2) and experimental values gave satisfactory agreement as shown in Figure 2. Inserting equation (2) into (1):

$$G_{IIC} = \frac{9a^2 P^2 C_b}{2b(2L^3 + 3a^3)} \quad (3)$$

where C_b is the compliance due to bending.

MODE I CRACK INITIATION AND EXTENSION

The fracture energy was observed to increase with crack extension from the teflon starter, Figure 3. The rise from an initiation value G_{IC} was found to coincide with the formation of a tied zone of bridged fibers which spanned the fracture surfaces. The amount of crack growth required to stabilize the tied zone effect was dependent on both moisture and temperature. At low temperatures, little fiber bridging took place and stabilization occurred soon after initiation.

The maximum or stabilized energy values, G_{IC}^S , were also utilized as a basis for comparison of both test and material variables. This stabilization of G_{IC} differs from the behaviour observed by other workers (11)(13) where the trans-laminar splitting fracture energy continuously increased with crack extension. The effects of ply orientation, temperature and moisture on the interlaminar fracture energy values are presented in Table I and Figure 4. Figure 5 shows the basic characteristics of the fracture surfaces.

Table 1. Fracture Energies as a Function of Ply Orientation for AS1/3501-6 (20°C/DRY).

Interface	0/0				+45/-45	90/90
	8	16	24	24**	22	22
G_{IC} (J/m ²)	123	-	126	132	99	138
G_{IC}^S (J/m ²)	173±2*	201±2	218±3	218	673	439

* Mean ± Std. error in mean.

** Voids 2.1 volume percent.

The initiation energy G_{IC} for AS1/3501-6 was found to be virtually independent of the test variables and to fall within the range of G_{IC} values for bulk epoxy resins as measured by Bascom et al (15). The slightly lower value for the +45/-45 delamination interface may have been due to nonuniform crack initiation along the notch root as suggested by fracture surface markings.

The high modulus fiber system, HMS/3501-6, was characterized by a significantly lower initiation energy. Fractographic examination revealed the presence of extensive fiber-matrix bond failures. A similar finding was made in the case of the GY70/5208 material.

Pronounced differences were found in the effects of the variables on the stabilized fracture energy values achieved during crack extension. G_{IC}^S for +45/-45 and 90/90 interlaminar cracking was two to three times greater than the values characteristic of the unidirectional material. These enhanced values coincided with considerable matrix crack branching and deviation as observed on the fracture surfaces. In fact, in the 90° ply specimens, cracking eventually shifted into an adjacent 0° ply where it continued at a corresponding lower G_{IC}^S value.

Over the temperature range -50°C to +100°C, G_{IC}^S almost doubled for AS1/3501-6, both in the dry and wet state. Consequently, a hot/wet environment will not provide the lowest fracture energy for crack extension in this composite system. Enhanced fiber bridging and matrix cracking were observed to occur at +100°C compared to -50°C where very little bridging and cracking took place.

Moisture content led to much smaller variations in G_{IC}^S . Nevertheless, except at the lowest temperature, moisture tended to increase the fracture energy of AS1/3501-6. In the case of the low interfacial strength system, GY70/5208, the reverse effect was observed. Apparently the interfacial bond is further degraded by moisture ingress.

The dependence of G_{IC}^S on laminate thickness was attributed to differences in the tied zone characteristics once stabilization had taken place. The thicker specimens were less compliant and allowed a greater degree of fiber bridging.

MODE II CRACK INITIATION AND EXTENSION

Mode II crack extension in the unidirectional material remained essentially coplanar with the starter notch. However, in the angle ply specimens, the crack deviated immediately towards the compression surface until it encountered a 0° ply: thereafter, shearing continued along the 0/90 or 0/45 interface. Consequently, the G_{IIC} values reported are characteristic of fracture originating from teflon starters placed on the 0/90 and 0/45 interfaces.

As the crack propagation in the shearing mode specimen was much less stable than in the opening mode case, only two fracture energy values were obtainable from each specimen - G_{IIC} , the initiation value for crack growth from the root of the teflon notch and G_{IIC}^v , a value for extension of the arrested initial crack which averaged approximately 25 mm in length.

The test results summarized in Table II show the effects of both temperature and the ply orientation along the delamination interface. The initiation energy values are seen to be significantly greater than those for mode I fracture. This finding was accompanied by the observation that the fracture surface characteristics, particularly the degree of matrix microcracking, changed substantially on re-initiating a mode II crack from an arrested mode I crack, Figure 6. Bascom et al (15) reported G_{IIC} values for bulk epoxy which were ten times greater than their measured G_{IC} values. Likewise, Wu (11) found G_{IIC} for transverse cracking in Scotch-ply to be approximately nine times larger than G_{IC} .

Table II. G_{IIC} as a Function of Temperature and Ply Orientation for AS1/3501-6 and HMS/3501-6 - DRY.

Fiber	No. Plys	Delamin. Interface	T (°C)	G_{IIC} (J/m ²) (Initiation)	G_{IIC}^I (J/m ²) ($\Delta a \approx 25$ mm)
AS1	24	0/0	20	452 ± 6*	385 ± 6
AS1	28	0/45	20	487 ± 21	387 ± 11
AS1	28	0/90	20	398 ± 27	358 ± 20
AS1	24	0/0	20**	504 ± 16	-
AS1	24	0/0	-50	556 ± 17	385 ± 6
AS1	24	0/0	100	405 ± 9	368 ± 7
HMS	24	0/0	20	152 ± 11	133

* Mean ± Std. error in mean; ** Voids 2.1 volume percent.

Although the scatter was not as great as observed by others (10), G_{IIC} was nevertheless more variant than G_{IC} . The findings suggest that for unidirectional AS1/3501-6, G_{IIC} decreases slightly with temperature in contrast to the independency displayed by G_{IC} . However, in greater contrast to the mode I case was the finding that the crack resistance, G_{IIC}^I , decreased with crack extension.

Ply orientation appeared to have little effect on either G_{IIC} or G_{IIC}^I although the fracture surfaces showed enhanced matrix cracking due to the cross-ply fibers, Figure 7. Fiber bridging was also observed to be present in the mode II specimens.

Once again, the HMS/3501-6 system displayed lower fracture energies due to the intrinsically weaker fiber-matrix bonds.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

The preliminary findings of the present work on AS1/3501-6 support the hypothesis that the toughness of the matrix phase is the primary controlling factor during crack initiation from an existing "clean" notch in the interlaminar plane subjected to mode I static loading. A "clean" notch would be one wherein no bridged fiber effects existed. Moisture and temperature will undoubtedly alter both the basic mechanical properties of the matrix as well as its residual stress state. As a consequence, the superposition of the applied stress on a variable residual stress field should be taken into account when measuring or comparing toughness characteristic of the unreinforced matrix (bulk or adhesive tests) with composite behaviour.

The importance of a sufficiently high fiber matrix interfacial bond strength in achieving at least a fracture initiation energy equivalent to that of the matrix was clearly demonstrated in the present work. Preferred delamination planes may be expected in hybrid structures containing HMS fibers.

A relatively unexplored mechanism in delamination fracture, fiber bridging, was shown to possess the capability of imparting a substantial increase in fracture energy during crack extension in mode I. Whether fiber bridging requires fabrication induced fiber misalignment as Wu (11) suggests or is a more fundamental outcome of matrix crack propagation in a complex stress field within the interlaminar plane remains to be shown. The bridgings do suggest a means other than matrix toughness enhancement (13) for increasing the relatively low crack initiation energies for opening mode delamination.

Regarding the mode II shear crack initiation energy, the results suggest that delamination cracking will be more strongly influenced by the tensile rather than the shear stresses. The finding that $G_{IIC} > G_{IC}$ is also of importance in establishing a failure criterion for mixed mode fracture (11).

Figure 1. Specimen Geometries for Mode I and Mode II Testing.

Figure 2. Comparison of Experimental Data with the Theoretical Compliance Curve for the Mode II Specimen Geometry.

Figure 3. Mode I Fracture Energy Versus Crack Extension from a Teflon Starter Notch for Unidirectional AS1/3501-6 and HMS/3501-6.

Figure 4. Mode I Stabilized Fracture Energy as a Function of Temperature and Moisture Content for Unidirectional AS1/3501-6 and GY70/5208.

Figure 5. Mode I Fracture Surfaces for AS1/3501-6, (a)(b)(c), and HMS/3501-6 (d). Crack Growth Left to Right. (560 X)

Figure 6. Fracture Surface of Unidirectional AS1/3501-6 at the Transition From Mode I Arrest (L) to Mode II Initiation (R). Cracking L to R. 20°C/DRY. (720 X)

Figure 7. Mode II Fracture Surfaces for AS1/3501-6 (20°C/DRY) (1120 X)

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